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Celia R. Ignacio, PhD

Faculty
Palawan State University
Narra, Palawan, Region IV-B, Philippines
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Noble Shame Begotten

Noble is the profession,
Noble is the service.
Dear teacher, started so noble and right,
Decided to lead a future promising and bright.

Hardships and stress, never a dismay,
Reporting for duty, happy and gay.
Display of learning completes the day;
For a teacher, it is a gold of hay.

Where art thou nobles, righteous and true?
Heroes whom people look up to?
Where art thou nobles, courageous and great,
Whose works of excellence flow in their fate?

The world is indeed bad and cruel;
It was then, and it is still now.
Where have the teachings gone?
Learnings seem undone.

Some are nobles no more;
Corrupt and greedy have taken over.
Models of erratic strategies,
Moral and shame put in silence.

Blame thrown to people in power,
Exercising their demons freely.
Perhaps it was the teachers they dear,
Who showed that one does not succeed fairly.

Look back at school, where cheating starts;
Bullying and oppression take part.

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True excellence reduced to naught,
Injustice and silence to the smart.

Remember the noble times,
When shame influenced acts;
When conscience thrived and lies never shined,
True knowledge and skills were divine.

Heroes should again rise,
Beat the villains so full of pretence.
Save the youth, their morals and being,
Save the world from wrong upbringing.

Let the callous feel the shame,
Let shame be in the frame.
As the nobles play in the game,
Let the right be given fame.